

THE REALIST-ENLIGHTENMENT TRADITION IN AZERBAIJANI LITERATURE: IN THE CONTEXT OF THE WORK OF S.S. AKHUNDOV, U. HAJIBEYOV AND A. SHAIG

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19979065>

ABSTRACT. *At the beginning of the 20th century, some Azerbaijani realist writers united around the press and publishing activities, while others (N. Vazirov, A. Hagverdiyev, U. Hajibeyov) worked in the field of theatre. Other realist-enlightenment writers, however, were engaged in children's literature on themes of education, teaching, and upbringing, creating realist-enlightenment literature. The entire creative activity of these teacher-writers was adapted to the needs of schools and education. Through their literary works, these writers complemented their pedagogical activities carried out in schools. Since realist-enlightenment writers regarded education, schools, and teachers as the most important means of national revival, they attached great importance to educational work. Therefore, the struggle for education, for school, and for upbringing occupied a central place in the work of those writers.*

Key words: *Azerbaijani literature, Enlightenment, realism, literary movement, Suleyman Sani Akhundov, Uzeyir Hajibeyov, Abdulla Shaig, Enlightenment movement, scary tales, publicist*

The first systematic theoretical classification concerning the stages of development of realism in Azerbaijani literary studies [3], as well as the profound scholarly interpretation of the issue of realism in the literature of the former Soviet Eastern peoples [4], emerged during the wave of literary discussions that took place in the 1960s.

Critical realists sought to awaken society by sharply criticizing and exposing the old social order, using satire to free people from outdated ways of thinking and mentality, portraying how feudal relations seriously hindered social development, and depicting the bitter truths of reality. Romanticists, on the other hand, were not satisfied merely with expressing hatred toward the disastrous scenes and inhuman values they observed in contemporary society; instead, they directed their thoughts toward the future and engaged in romantic appeals. Against the painful life of the past, romantics envisioned a hopeful, joyful, and bright world.

Enlightenment realists were not excessively absorbed in criticizing the past, nor did they construct dreams about the future. They mostly depicted ordinary, everyday concerns of life and, above all, turned to schools as the primary means for creating the future. They considered schools not only as a means for culture and revival but also as the main instrument for reforming the social order. They greatly exaggerated the significance of schools and saw salvation precisely in them.

Mirza Fatali Akhundzadeh and his enlightenment-minded contemporaries played a major role in elevating enlightenment from the level of an idea to that of a movement. Intellectuals who closely knew Mirza Fatali Akhundzadeh and supported his ideas were active in the principal spheres that shaped and developed the enlightenment environment [3, p.3].

“Aldanmış Kavakib,” the first example of large-scale realist prose in the history of Azerbaijani literature and the first specimen of the novella genre, exerted a powerful influence on the development of national literature in the 19th and 20th centuries through its ideological content and artistic qualities” [4, p.118].

Among the prominent representatives of enlightenment realism were Uzeyir Hajibeyov, Nariman Narimanov, Suleyman Sani Akhundov, Abdulla Shaig, Sultanmajid Ganizadeh, and Rashid bey Efendiyev. These writers shared the same goals, ideological orientation, sphere of activity, and thematic scope. Many of them such as S.S. Akhundov and A. Shaig were born into intellectual families of their time. The principal sphere of activity for these writers was the school. Unlike the traditional education and upbringing they themselves had received, they supported the “usuli-jadid” school system, advocating modern methods of education and upbringing. Enlightenment realists spread their ideas and ideals through schools, which served as the largest and most suitable audience for them. They read their literary works in schools and staged their dramas on school stages.

The literary and artistic heritage of the enlightenment writer S.S. Akhundov, one of the major representatives of Azerbaijani realist prose, occupies a distinctive place in the history of Azerbaijani literature and culture. S.S. Akhundov was born in 1875 in the city of Shusha into a noble family. His upbringing and education were supervised by his uncle, the well-known educator Safarali bey Valibeyov. In 1885, he entered the primary school attached to the Gori Teachers’ Seminary, and after graduating from the seminary in 1894, he began his teaching career in Baku. Like A. Shaig, J. Ganizadeh, M.A. Sabir, and others, he encountered numerous difficulties in the development of public education. Nevertheless, by working in the fields of education, literature, and culture, he made serious efforts toward raising the younger generation in a new spirit and overcoming backwardness and stagnation.

In 1906, he actively participated in the First Teachers’ Congress convened in Baku, proposed useful initiatives for the reform of the Arabic alphabet, and was elected a member of the commission established at the congress to prepare educational programs in the native language. In 1908, together with A. Shaig, M. Mahmudbeyov, and other educational figures, he compiled the textbook “Second Year.” In addition, he published his literary works in the journals “Dabistan” and “Maktab.” Having devoted many years to pedagogical activity, S.S. Akhundov passed away in Baku in 1932.

Having emerged from the realist literary school of M.F. Akhundov, Suleyman Sani became known in the history of our socio-literary thought as a master of the short story, a playwright, a public teacher, and a cultural figure.

He began his literary career in 1899 with the comedy “Tamahkar” (“The Greedy One”), written under the influence of M.F. Akhundov’s comedy “Haji Gara.” In this comedy, the writer deeply perceived the “contradiction between life events and the essence and meaning of life” within feudal society and created original examples of social comedy. Through the work “Tamahkar,” S.S. Akhundov not only exposed the negative aspects of his era, but also, through positive characters such as Imran, Gulzar, and Sharaf khanim who opposed feudal traditions called upon people to show self-sacrifice and build a better life [5].

The comedy “Tamahkar” was written against greed and stinginess, criticizing these negative human traits through humor. The negative comic hero of the work is Haji Murad. One of the strongest aspects of the playwright’s realism lies in his portrayal of Haji Murad’s memorable characteristics his stinginess, greed, cowardice, and hypocrisy through the unity of

his words and actions. The writer does not merely expose and ridicule the negative traits of his satirical character; he also extends the miser's moral pettiness and negativity to the social class to which he belongs. To generalize this feature, the playwright contrasts Haji Murad with another miser, Maharram bey. Through this comparison, the moral ugliness, greed, and stinginess of both negative types become fully apparent.

Eradicating greed, stinginess, envy, deceitfulness, and other negative traits from human nature cannot be accomplished by the literature of a single era or by only a few artists. The miserly character Haji Murad in “Tamahkar” is a product of the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. He is a typical artistic representation of the period in Azerbaijan when capitalist social relations and bourgeois connections were emerging and when money and usury were gradually gaining widespread influence. Haji Murad's main ideal is wealth, and the object of his belief and worship is money. His excessive greed for money has destroyed everything good within him and left him only with negative qualities.

S.S. Akhundov became recognized as a prose writer through the publication of his “Terrifying Tales” (“Qorxulu nağıllar”) in the journal “Maktab” between 1912 and 1914. The series includes five works: “Ahmad and Malayka,” “Abbas and Zaynab,” “Nuraddin,” “The Dark-Skinned Girl,” and “Ashraf.” These works, which describe the lives of children, were written in the form of folk tales in order to meet schoolchildren's need for artistic reading and aesthetic education.

Four of the stories (with the exception of “The Dark-Skinned Girl”) are narrated by Haji Samad, a man who loves education and culture. The events he tells his children, Mahammad and Fatma, are drawn from the miserable life of the past and are filled with frightening incidents that terrify children; therefore, the works are called “Terrifying Tales.”

The story “Ahmad and Malayka” tells about a poor family head named Nuraddin. In order to provide for his family, Nuraddin goes to the city, but his tragic death devastates the family and forces them to live in severe hardship. A traveler named Jamaladdin, who helps this family, wins admiration as a humanitarian figure. Through this, the writer instills in readers humanistic feelings such as helping those in need. The author conveys to young readers that there are many kind and well-intentioned people in life, and that one should learn from them and take them as examples. Thus, the idea of humanism and the belief that it is not angels but people themselves who become saviors in life form the central message of the story.

In the story “Abbas and Zaynab,” the writer addresses a serious social problem, seeing ignorance and the cruel, merciless behavior of people in society as consequences of illiteracy. He depicts the fanaticism and ignorance of a bandit named Safar, who devastates a village in order to avenge his brother, as well as the tragic deaths of the siblings Abbas and Zaynab. The educational impact of the story is reflected in its motifs of struggling against illiteracy, backwardness, and lack of culture. The writer attempts to awaken in readers an interest in science and education, while also inspiring hatred toward ignorance and the brutality arising from it.

In “Terrifying Tales,” (“Qorxulu nağıllar”) S.S. Akhundov portrays upbringing, especially healthy family upbringing, as one of the most important factors guiding human life. In this respect, his story “Nuraddin” is particularly characteristic. The protagonist of this story also comes from the poor social class, and the events are drawn from the lives of orphaned children. The plotline of the work is based on folk proverbs such as “Goodness never disappears” and “Do good and you will see its reward.” In the story, not only responding to goodness with goodness

but also repaying evil with goodness is brought to the forefront. However, this weakens the idea of human struggle in life and the search for ways out of difficulties, leaving a person at the mercy of fate and destiny.

The story “The Dark-Skinned Girl” (“Qaraca qız”), written by the author in 1913, became the masterpiece of his creativity and brought him great fame. The main character of the story, the dark-skinned girl Tutu, is not very different from the heroes of the author’s earlier stories. In this work, the writer artistically substantiates the moral-pedagogical idea that education and upbringing have a tremendous transformative role in life, and that through upbringing a person can acquire any character traits and habits. There is no uneducable character or irredeemable person in life; however, education should not be based on violence, but rather on reason, patience, and a progressive educational system.

In the story “Ashraf,” through the character of Ashraf, the tragedy of a child separated from homeland and family, longing for his native land and people, and issues of education and upbringing are artistically generalized. In the writer’s depiction, the problem of proper and healthy moral upbringing comes to the forefront: the educated and well-mannered mother Najiba raises a child like Ashraf. The enlightenment-minded writer emphasizes that humanitarian individuals emerge among intellectuals and that such people show genuine human compassion toward those in need.

Uzeyir Hajibeyov (1885–1948), the founder of Azerbaijani national opera, writer, and publicist, occupies a unique place in the history of our literary and artistic thought. As the author of numerous operas and comedies, U. Hajibeyov regarded the development of education, theatre, and culture as one of the main factors of revival and progress. With the opera “Leyli and Majnun,” written in 1907, he laid the foundation of Azerbaijani national opera art.

Understanding the essence of satirical literature and humor, U. Hajibeyov highly appreciated the educational significance of musical comedy in social life. His musical comedies “Husband and Wife” (1909), “If Not That One, Then This One” (1910), and “Arshin Mal Alan” (1913) introduced him not only as a composer but also as a playwright whose works were infused with humor.

Hajibeyov’s mastery as a dramatist lies in his ability to portray ordinary domestic issues in unity with major social problems and to express profound ideas and aims of his era within comic situations. Behind the household scenes, contemporary society appears together with all its contradictions, social classes, struggles, and conflicts.

“Husband and Wife,” written in 1909, was the first Azerbaijani musical comedy. The comic conflict in the work is built upon the quarrel between husband and wife, which also serves as the source of humor. The primary targets of satire and criticism in the comedy are Marjan bey and Karbalayi Gubad. The issues of women’s freedom and healthy family relations are raised as serious social concerns.

Hajibeyov’s comedy “If Not That One, Then This One,” written in 1910, is considered one of the classical works in the history of Azerbaijani dramaturgy. The ruthless criticism of bourgeois society, built and dominated by money, immediately attracts attention in the comedy. Relationships between money and love, money and family, and money and society encompass the entire plot of the work. From Mashadi Ibad and Rustam bey to the humble porter, everyone is preoccupied with money. A father sells his beloved daughter to an unworthy man for money; the merchant Mashadi Ibad is grateful to money for all his “successes,” and it is money that humiliates him in old age and leads him onto the difficult “paths of love.”

Young characters such as Sarvar and Gulnaz represent the progressive-minded youth of the era, persistently struggling to eliminate the flaws and ugliness present in family life and morality. The comedy mainly derives its humor from the contradictory subject of unequal marriages arranged without love or mutual understanding and from their consequences. The desire of a fifty-year-old man to marry a teenage girl through the power of his wealth, along with his impatience and exaggerated efforts in pursuit of this goal, creates comic situations. Thanks to the intelligent, courageous, and humorous plan of Sarvar, one of the positive heroes of the comedy, Mashadi Ibad fails to achieve his aim, and having lost everything, he is humiliated because of his moral pettiness.

Hajibeyov's comedy "Arshin Mal Alan" (1913) brought the author great fame; it was translated into nearly fifty foreign languages and staged in many countries around the world. In this comedy, Hajibeyov contrasts new ways of forming a family with old traditions and patriarchal customs. Through the character of the merchant Asgar, he rejects outdated traditions and promotes the idea that family life should be based on love and on truly knowing the person one intends to marry.

Alongside Asgar, who represents the young generation of the period, the character Gulchokra symbolizing unhappy girls forced into marriage also seeks to take a new and courageous step against outdated family relations. This sacred aspiration and the persistent struggle for it ensure the triumph of the new over the old in the comedy.

One of the realist-enlightenment writers, Abdulla Shaig (1881–1959), occupies a unique place in the history of twentieth-century literary thought through his creative activity. Alongside his pedagogical work, he was also engaged in literary creation, writing lyrical poems, prose, and dramatic works. During the first period of his творчество (1905–1920), he gained fame as the author of numerous poems, prose works, and dramas. During these years, he wrote works such as "The Engaged Girl," "Address to the Twentieth Century," "The Fairy of Freedom," "Remember," "Tubercular Life," "The Sultan of Mountains," "We Are All Particles of One Sun," "Adham," "The Destruction of Two Families," and "Ideal and Humanity," as well as the stories "The Letter Did Not Arrive," "Migration," "Lamentation," and "Dursun."

In Shaig's poetry of this period, alongside lyrics mainly devoted to sorrowful scenes, there are also hopeful passages written in the spirit of turning toward the future and light. These two lines coexist in the poet's works not in active conflict but side by side. The first line is the lyricism of grief and sorrow, while the second line is a pleasant dream and bright romanticism. The sadness in A. Shaig's poetry is not accidental; it is social sorrow, civic sorrow.

As one of the progressive intellectuals of his era, A. Shaig strove to rescue his people from ignorance and to promote the opening of modern-style schools. His mind was constantly occupied with ideas of a free and cultured life, contemporary social issues, and the sufferings and needs of the people. In the poems written between 1907 and 1912, this sorrow becomes even stronger because reactionary forces at that time dominated with full power, mercilessly persecuting progressive-minded people, thoughts, and feelings.

In his poem with the refrain "In the Form," he expresses his emotions, the way they manifested themselves, and how they oppressed his soul:

The vast shining sandy shore waving in the distance,
My heart rolling between hope and mourning,
Appears before my eyes like a mirage,
Cries within me like a broken rubab. [10]

In his poem “The Engaged Girl,” he depicts the tragedy and cries of a Muslim girl whose youthful feelings and dignity are trampled upon and who is forcibly made the “spouse” of a savage man:

O my fate, do not torment me so,
Why should I drink blood from a golden bowl?
My lament makes the mountains and stones weep.
Alas, my father extinguished my light!
I am alone, alas, with no helper,
A bud has become the companion of a thorn! [10]

The same cry can also be felt in the poems “The Fairy of Freedom,” “Remember,” and “Tubercular Life.” The poet is overwhelmed by darkness, ignorance, misery, and grief. He explains the reason for this sorrow in his poem “Fragments” with the lines: “What burns my heart is only this: I did not see my homeland as I wished.” This is the sorrow and longing of a citizen who wishes to see his homeland worthy of the world of high culture and his people among the advanced nations of the century.

When A. Shaig does not see his homeland “as his heart desires,” he becomes sorrowful, yet this sorrow does not lead him to pessimism or despair. Above all, it compels him to reflect. Eventually, he sees a light and hope, and this hope becomes a great consolation and a support for his future struggle and activity.

A. Shaig’s prose works “The Letter Did Not Arrive” (1908), “Migration” (1910), and “Dursun” (1911) were original literary phenomena. “The Letter Did Not Arrive” is a work devoted to the oil industry, the exploitation and lack of rights of workers, realistically reflecting the events of the period. A worker named Gurban, who came from Iran, works in the oil fields, enduring all hardships and performing heavy and dangerous labor in order to slightly improve the living conditions of his family in Iran and provide for his children.

Escaping the painful and difficult life in Iran to earn bread in Baku, Gurban works day and night in Haji Gulu’s oil fields. As a father, he constantly longs for his children and never forgets their difficult and needy life. He is unable to send the letter he writes to his family and dies in an oil well. Yet Haji Gulu thinks not about his death, but about the wealth he will gain from the oil flowing from the well.

At that time, such an event was not accidental in the oil fields; it was an ordinary, everyday occurrence. Gurban is a typical representative of ignorant workers who do not struggle for their rights, accept their existing life as fate, and live only through the limits of their labor and their private lives

SUMMARY

Thus, realist-enlightenment literature, which took shape at the beginning of the twentieth century, constituted an important stage in the history of Azerbaijani socio-literary thought. The main characteristic of this literary movement was the organic combination of the ideas of school, education, and upbringing with artistic creativity, as well as the presentation of education as the decisive means for the renewal of society and the achievement of national revival. The study demonstrates that, unlike the representatives of critical realism and romanticism, enlightenment realist writers neither became absorbed in harsh criticism of the past nor limited themselves to utopian visions of the future. Instead, they focused primarily on real-life problems and their

practical solutions especially solutions achieved through schools and educational upbringing. The promotion of moral-educational ideas, humanism, and enlightenment principles in the stories and dramas of S.S. Akhundov, the exposure of social contradictions through humor and satire in the musical comedies of U. Hajibeyov and the unity of pedagogical thought with artistic representation in the works of A. Shaig together ensure the ideological and aesthetic integrity of realist-enlightenment literature. The works of these writers demonstrate that the school was regarded not merely as an institution that provides knowledge, but also as the principal institution carrying out the moral and social transformation of society. Consequently, realist-enlightenment literature in Azerbaijani literary history was not only an artistic and aesthetic phenomenon, but also an important component of the socio-pedagogical movement. It exerted a significant influence on the formation of national consciousness and on the creation of a new model of human being and society. From this perspective, the works of S.S. Akhundov, U. Hajibeyov and A. Shaig should be evaluated as a valuable and enduring legacy of both our literary and enlightenment history.

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